

Path2Integrity trainer questionnaire

Instructions

In this evaluation, we kindly ask you to respond to the following statements about the training you conducted.

The survey is designed to be additive to other evaluation instruments which should be compared with each other. This requires a code generated by you, which will be anonymised by us before analysing the data, so that no conclusions can be drawn about your person. We do not collect or store your IP addresses.

Group specific

Please enter the two-digit group code of the identification code you have agreed on with the participants. [Please write your answer here:](#)

Which target group was taught? [Please choose only one of the following:](#)

- Secondary school students
- Bachelor students
- Master students
- Early career researchers
- Senior researchers
- Mixed
- If none of these, please write it down

Which academic discipline(s) were the participants from? [Please choose all that apply:](#)

- Interdisciplinary
- Natural Sciences
- Engineering and Technology
- Medical and Health Sciences
- Agricultural Sciences
- Social Sciences
- Humanities
- Arts
- Other:

Was the course voluntary or mandatory for the participants? [Please choose only one of the following:](#)

- Voluntary
- Mandatory
- I don't know.

How was the training conducted? [Please choose only one of the following:](#)

- Online
- Face-to-face
- Blended
- Other

How many participants did you have on average? [Please write your answer here:](#)

Which learning unit(s) did you conduct with your group? [Please indicate the order by using drag and drop in the list on the right side. Your first learning unit should be on the top, moving through to your latest one.](#)

On average, how high was the participants' workload per learning unit in minutes (all together)? [Please write your answer here:](#)

On average, how much time did you spent for the preparation of one learning unit? [Please write your answer here:](#)

Was or is the Path2Integrity campaign (e.g. posters, leaflets, brochures, banners) carried out at your institution? [Please choose only one of the following:](#)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Did you use other Path2Integrity materials except the learning units? If yes, please select. [Please choose all that apply:](#)

- Path2Integrity Flyers
- Path2Integrity Posters
- Path2Integrity Roadmap
- Path2Integrity Videos
- Other:

Do you think your trainees are more confident about research integrity after the training? [Please choose only one of the following:](#)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Organisational and cultural obstacles

In order to guarantee data protection, we ask you to refrain from statements that make it possible to identify a participant. Please use general statements.

What went especially well during the training you conducted with this group? [Please write your answer here:](#)

What problems or obstacles (e.g. organisational or cultural) were encountered in the preparation and implementation of the training? [Please write your answer here:](#)

What were the underlying issues or barriers which caused the aforementioned problems and obstacles to occur? [Please write your answer here:](#)

How did you solve these problems? [Please write your answer here:](#)

What needs – in terms of resources, support, etc. – appeared during the training? [Please write your answer here:](#)

Rating

Please rate the learning output of your participants with regard to the following aspects. My participants ...

Rate each item between ++ and -- with ++ being „Strongly agree“ and -- being „Strongly disagree“.

	++	+	0	-	--
have an increased awareness on research integrity topics.					
can apply research integrity principles in cases.					
have a better understanding of research integrity principles.					
can apply research integrity principles and regulations on cases.					
developed reasoning and argumentation skills regarding research integrity.					
improved their critical thinking.					
can search and find relevant research integrity resources.					
have become more confident in dealing with research integrity issues.					

Please rate the following statements. Regarding the training you conducted with your participants.

Rate each item between ++ and -- with ++ being „Strongly agree“ and -- being „Strongly disagree“.

	++	+	0	-	--
The duration of the learning units was appropriate.					
There were enough opportunities for the participants to express their opinions freely.					
I need further support as educator to use the Path2Integrity learning units.					
I feel I have enough knowledge to use the Path2Integrity learning units in my teaching.					
I feel I have enough skills to use the Path2Integrity learning units in my teaching.					
I would recommend the learning units to other trainers or lecturers.					
I feel confident enough as educator in using the whole Path2Integrity materials.					
I would incorporate the Path2Integrity materials in my regular research integrity teaching.					

If you have a negative rating on one of the items above, how would you improve this?

Please write your answer here:

Further Information

Which learning units have worked most efficiently in your opinion? Please tell us, why they worked so well in your opinion. [Comment only when you choose an answer. Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:](#)

What other Path2Integrity materials did you find particularly useful and why? [Please write your answer here:](#)

How would you improve the learning units for future trainings? [Please write your answer here:](#)

If you have some comments or suggestions for improvement, please feel free to write them down. [Please write your answer here:](#)